

Time Base Force (Impulse) Versus Space Based Force ($-dV/dx$) in Classical and Quantum Mechanics

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If one considers two colliding particles in a center-of-mass frame, each with different mass, then they have equal and opposite momentum or energy flow. After the collision, they also have equal and opposite momenta. A similar idea holds for a particle breaking, with force, into two pieces of different mass. It seems that a force, equal and opposite strength but existing only for a period of time, pushes the two unequal mass particles apart. Thus, time is broken into equal portions in an impulse type reaction. From this one may obtain Newton's second law. Newton's law, however, is usually applied to a space based force i.e. $F(x)=-dV/dx$, so the same law holds for impulse type forces as well as space based ones.

In classical statistical mechanics with a potential $V(x)$, one has both impulse (time-based forces) as well as a space-based one. The impulse (time-based force) creates the equilibrium. In quantum mechanics, one begins with a space based force $F(x)=-dV/dx$ or $V(x)$ a space based potential. We argue in this note that $V(x)$ is actually linked to a time-based (impulse picture) in classical mechanics with the $V(x)$ picture being of a statistical nature i.e. $dp = \text{Integral } -dV/dx dx/v(x)$ where $1/v(x)$ ($v(x)$ =velocity) is proportional to the spatial classical density. We also try to link the sharpness of $V(x)$ to space resolution and momentum.

In quantum mechanics, one tries to create a statistical theory based on free particles which undergo impulse hits or a time based force. Thus, a space based force (related to $V(x)$) is converted into a series of impulse (time-based force hits). Unlike classical statistical mechanics, one does not have the two separate kinds of forces (time and space). The time based (impulse hits) must create an average appearance of a space based force ($-dV/dx$). How may this be done while maintaining a momentum based space resolution? Impulse (time based force hits) occur anywhere in space so a kind of mapping of the time based impulse hit to space must be done. This may be done through $\exp(ikx)$ where k is the momentum hit delivered by a time-based force which has a spatial wavelength proportional to $1/k$. Thus, different $\exp(ikx)$ with weights (which are actually time-based impulses acting at any point x) may create the appearance of a spatially based force $-dV(x)/dx$. This, however, has implications on the probability of the particle $P(p,x)$. We try to investigate these ideas in this note.

Newton's Law and Conservation of Momentum

Conservation of momentum is an important idea, with momentum being energy flow. In non-relativistic mechanics, it is mv (with m_0 being energy to first order) while in special relativity it is $(m_0/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}) v$ i.e. full energy flow. How may one see momentum conservation in a collision of two particles? First, consider an object which breaks forcefully into two particles with different mass. These particles may move out with opposite velocities after a force stops acting on them (as the object breaks up). In such a case, if one considers mass to be a kind of energy (to first order), then mv is energy flow. If one runs a film of this process backwards, one sees two particles moving backwards until they combine into one object. This

object has no energy flow, so it may be reasonable to say that the energy flow of each particle should cancel i.e. one should have momentum conservation.

It seems there will be a push on each particle as the object breaks up. One may suggest that this push is a force which has the same magnitude of push on each particle of different mass at each instant in time until it “turns” off after the object has fully broken and the two particles are each moving with different constant velocities. The idea of equal and opposite forces on each particle makes sense if one considers the force to be a kind of trapped tension within the object. Again one may run a movie backwards so having different magnitudes of forces on each particle is problematic as the particles reunite to become an object.

$$\text{Thus: } \Delta p = \text{change in energy flow} = \int F(t) dt \quad ((1))$$

Here, one has a time-based force which has the same value at each time t as the object breaks up. One may note that each particle moves with different speeds (as they have different masses). Thus, one may replace t in $F(t)$ in terms of x differently for each particle i.e. $x_1(t)$ versus $x_2(t)$. Each particle would see a different spatial force.

One may use ((1)) to write Newton’s second law i.e.

$$dp/dt = F(t) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) applies to a time-based force, but a particle has a trajectory $x(t)$ so one may find $t(x)$. Then ((2)) becomes:

$$dp/dt = F(x) \quad ((3))$$

Usually, one considers problems in which $F(x)$ is the same through x for all particles. As argued above, however, this does not hold for impulse based (time based forces). One may ask how this affects classical statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

In classical statistical mechanics (e.g. a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas), equilibrium is created through two-body elastic collisions. These are impulse based hits (i.e. time based force). If one introduces an overall potential $V(x)$, it is a space based force which affects density, but does not change the time-based (impulse based) force (two-body collision) nature of the equilibrium. It only creates a spatial density.

Two Classical Scenarios of Force

In the above sections, we argued that in classical mechanics, there are two different scenarios for the action of force. The first is the idea of an impulse [$\int dt F(t)$] which is physically manifested when a ball is struck and receives a momentum. In this scenario, time is key and is broken into equally spaced units dt .

In the second scenario, spatial motion is key as space is divided into equally spaced units dx and one considers acceleration at each point x . It should be noted that within a region dx , a particle is said to have velocity $v(x)$.

How does one reconcile these two scenarios? Force is described as a push or pull and so apparently has physical meaning by itself. This seems to lean towards the impulse picture which multiplies force by dt and yields a change in momentum dp . (This is also keeping with conservation of momentum). This change in momentum is independent of the velocity of the particle before it was struck. The acceleration picture multiplies F by dx to yield work done, but this depends on the initial velocity of the incoming particle. Specifically:

$$dp/dt = F \rightarrow dp = \int F(x) dx/v(x) \quad ((3a))$$

One may see that dp in the acceleration picture depends directly on $v(x)$ (velocity). $1/v(x)$ plays the role of a kind of classical spatial density (unnormalized). It may be noticed that dx , although being small in classical physics, is large enough to incorporate a large portion of a quantum system at high energy. Thus, the correspondence principle links $1/v(x)$ to the quantum spatial density.

The same force $F(x)$ acts over dx , but a fast particle is present less of the time in dx than a slow one and so somehow receives less of a dp . This appears to be a statistical picture because it is as if the force is trying to change dp for a large p , but is somehow having less of a probability in doing so because the particle moves out of dx so quickly. This seems to suggest that force is somehow linked to time. It takes a dt for it to render an effect of dp regardless of incoming p . Thus, we argue that the classical acceleration picture already contains the time-dependent impulse picture and is also statistical.

As we have argued in a previous note (1), there seems to be a spatial frequency linked to momentum. A sharp derivative $-dV/dx$ means a high force which should be a physical concept. One needs high spatial resolution to see this sharp derivative which is related to a high dp (which is constant in the impulse scenario with respect to incoming momentum). As a result, one may suggest that a $V(x)$ with a sharp derivative (i.e. a high force) is linked to a high momentum transfer. Is there a way to retain an acceleration picture ($V(x)$) and at the same keep impulse hits which seem to be present and maintain dp linked to high spatial resolution? This seems to suggest a periodic function in p as a possible solution i.e. $\exp(ikx)$ where k really means dk i.e. the impulse given which does not have to be small (i.e. k instead of dk).

As a result, a mapping occurs to a two dimensional space in which k is a frequency that creates spatial resolution. As a result, one may write $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. In order for this to have meaning, $\exp(ikx)$ must augment the momentum of a particle by k . It thus appears that a particle may be represented by $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. it too has a momentum resolution (which is experimentally observable). This seems reasonable because it was argued that momentum is linked to spatial resolution. A sharp $V(x)$ derivative delivers a high dp to a particle and this resolution is "carried" by the particle. In other words: $\exp(ipx)\exp(ikx) = \exp(i(p+k)x)$.

How can one describe a particle by $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. a two-vector or complex number representing a unit length rotating through space with momentum p ? In classical statistical mechanics, this is not done. One has $P(p)$ which is a real number (assuming $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to some kind of probability). As argued in a previous note (1), even in the impulse picture in a statistical setting,

a particle with momentum p is at the same changing into another p_1 . It only makes sense to talk of $P(p)$, we argue, if there is a balanced reversed reaction which creates a p from p_1 . This occurs in classical statistical mechanics, but not in quantum mechanics where the impulse hit is between $\exp(ipx)$ and the potential piece $V_k \exp(ikx)$ and does not have an equal time-reversed part.

Quantum Bound States

What happens in quantum bound states? The space based $V(x)$ scenario is changed to a time-based force (impulse) scenario. The time-based force scenario is the actual physical scenario which produces an average which appears as if one has the space based $V(x)$. Thus, one must be able to decompose $V(x)$ into a set of time-based impulse hits. One might at first propose:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k(x) \text{ [impulse hit of } k] \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is a hybrid of an acceleration picture through $V_k(x)$ and of impulse hits. To have a picture strictly based on impulse hits one needs:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k \text{ [impulse hit of } k] \quad ((4))$$

$V(x)$ is a function of x so [impulse hit of k] must contain x , yet impulse forces should be time based hits at any x . A solution is to have a periodic $\exp(ikx)$, as noted above. This delivers hits of k at any x , yet may create any $V(x)$. A given x is a kind of frequency in momentum space for different k values. If $\exp(ikx)$ is to deliver k momentum hits at any point x , a particle in a momentum state p , should be of the form $\exp(ipx)$. This is also invariant over all of space. Then $\exp(ikx)\exp(ipx) = \exp(i(p+k)x)$. A particle having a probability form of $\exp(ipx)$ has physical consequences because $W(x) = \text{Sum } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ may be a periodic function if it satisfies:

$$\{\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) p p / 2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((5))$$

Using $W^*(x)W(x)$ as a recipe for spatial density (because $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ i.e. represents overall probability), yields a physical spatial density which has humps.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the idea of time-based force (impulse) and an acceleration picture $V(x)$ both exist in classical mechanics. Furthermore, the acceleration picture seems to contain a statistical treatment of the impulse picture i.e. $dp = \text{Integral } F(x) dx / v(x)$ where $1/v(x)$ ($v(x)$ =velocity) is the unnormalized spatial density at x . Thus, the acceleration picture is a statistical picture based on impulse, we argue, so in a quantum scenario it seems reasonable to use an impulse picture and yet insist that on average it reproduce $V(x)$. How may this be done? We argue that classically, a sharp $V(x)$ at x (i.e. a high d/dx derivative) yields a large dp in the

impulse picture regardless of the incoming p . Thus, a high k impulse hit (k =momentum) is linked with sharp spatial resolution. In a statistical picture of free particles, this k hit may occur at any x , but must preserve the high x resolution. This seems to lead to $\exp(ikx)$ as a mechanism of k momentum delivery at any point while retaining high resolution. $V(x)$ may then be created on average as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. A quantum particle with momentum p should also have a high spatial resolution and accept a k hit at any point x i.e. be of the form $\exp(ipx)$ so that $\exp(ipx)\exp(ikx)=\exp(i(p+k)x)$. Given such a statistical picture, how may $\exp(ipx)$ be associated with probability? It is complex (two-dimensional). We argue (as in (1)), that in classical statistical mechanics $P(p)$ makes sense as a real number. Furthermore, $P(p)$ holds at each x i.e. one has $P(p)P_1(x)$ where $P_1(x)$ is the spatial density and an overall normalization is needed. A momentum p receives an impulse and changes into a p_1 , suggesting a dual nature of p - p_1 , but there is a balanced time-reversed reaction which converts p_1 into p and breaks this dual nature. In quantum bound states in which p receives a k hit from $V_k \exp(ikx)$, there is no such time reversed balanced part and so one cannot really talk of $P(p,x)$ as a real value. A quantum particle has a multi-nature. It may be p or be in the process of reacting with a k_i from $V_{k_i} \exp(i k_i x)$ forming a $p+k_i$ state. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is not a problem in that sense.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Wavefunction and the Identity of a Momentum State in a Quantum Bound State (preprint, zenodo, 2021)